

ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND GOVERNANCE PRACTICES ON PERFORMANCE OF MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA

Hilary Emeka Afodigbueokwu (ACA), Abosade Kerry- Taiwo and Idowu Lawrence Adewusi (PhD)

University of Ulster, Birmingham, Campus, United Kingdom

E-mail: Afodigbueokwu-HE@ulster.ac.uk, kerry_Taiwo-A@ulster.ac.uk, I.adewusi@ulster.ac.uk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15586360>

Abstract: *This study determined the effect of environmental, social and governance practices on performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the environmental practices, Social practices and corporate governance practices as the independent variables and cash value added for dependent variable. Data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms in Nigeria from 2012 to 2023. Hypotheses were tested inferential statistics regression analysis. From the hypotheses results, environmental disclosure had a negative coefficient but statistically significant at 5% level for Nigeria manufacturing firms; Social practice disclosure had a positive coefficient which was significant at 5% level for Nigeria manufacturing firms; Governance practices disclosure had a negative coefficient but was significant at 5% level for Nigeria manufacturing firms. Based on the outcome of the study, the study recommended among others that though the social disclosure revealed positive significant, Nigerian government agencies should make corresponding penalties for enterprises with poor social practice performance and put forward equivalent refinement ideas for enterprises with good social practice.*

Keywords: *Environmental practices, Social practices, corporate governance practices and cash value added*

Introduction

Firms are keener to publish information on their environmental, social and corporate governance principles engagement and use ESG as a means to share information on business sustainability with their stakeholders (Chang & Lee, 2022). Among the directions of this approach is a focus on indicators to measure results related to an organization's involvement in addressing environmental and social issues or implementing policies with an impact on corporate governance. These indicators are grouped in the ESG (Environment – Social – Governance) categories that integrate the results of companies' environmental, social and governance activities (Veenstra & Ellemers, 2020).

On the other hand, finding a balance between increasing financial performance and the complex and high expectations of different stakeholders is a challenge for business managers. They must prioritize long-term and short-term objectives and sometimes forego maximizing short-term financial performance to meet urgent corporate social and environmental objectives. This balance is often achieved when the cost of minimizing the negative environmental and social impact of company operations do not lead to compromising corporate financial performance (Busch et al., 2011). Therefore, an increasingly relevant subject and research theme is the analysis of the link between ESG and organizational performance reported by companies.

Consistent with the government's aspiration in the Economic Transformation Programme (ETP) to achieve its developed status, this study considers a contemporary measure of financial performance which is multidimensional. In contrast to single-dimensional measures of corporate performance, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), a mathematical-programming method that incorporates multiple variables (Cooper, Seiford, & Tone, 2006), provides a comprehensive performance measure. Various attributes can be evaluated simultaneously to calculate an efficiency score for a decision-making unit (DMU). In other words, a holistic performance evaluation that provides aggregated activities information can be done via DEA (Homburg, 2001). Taken together, this study ascertains the effect of ESG on efficiency, which is considered in a holistic manner.

The need for consistent, decisive environmental accounting principles has been argued in professional circles for some time, but perhaps never better illustrated than right now as thick black oil continues to gush out in several parts of the world including Nigeria and Ghana. The environmental effect has obviously been calamitous as television screens record images of marine wildlife floating in a brown blob of oil around many areas of the world. This represents a loss of nature's carrying capacity, which also entails damage from an accounting perspective. Interesting research gaps concerning ESG relationships remain unresolved. The relationship between ESG and effects on economic performance (EP) is still controversial, a matter for further inquiry (Nasrallah & El Khoury, 2021).

Adeneye and Kammoun (2022) undertook a study titled 'Real earnings management and capital structure: Does Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) performance matter?'. Velte (2019) conducted a study titled 'The bidirectional relationship between ESG performance and earnings management—empirical evidence from Germany'. Fazle, Ruzlin and Jeaneth (2021) Purpose – The purpose of this study is to explore the impact of sustainability (environmental, social and governance or ESG) practices on the financial performance (FP) of the Nordic financial industry. The study covers a sample selection of observations for a total of 152 firm years for 39 financial companies within the Nordic region (Sweden, Denmark, Finland and Norway) for the business years including 2015–2019. Data regarding ESG and FP indicators were extracted from the Thomson Reuters Eikon database in July 2020. This is a quantitative study using regression and a generalized method of moments. Using

static and dynamic estimators, the authors found both positive and negative impacts of sustainability practice on FP.

However, these prior studies mainly proxied corporate performance with return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), earning per share (EPS) and Tobin's Q, more so there is a dearth study on cash value added by the prior related studies as another variable for economic performance.

The main objective of this study is to assess the effect of environmental, social and governance practices on economic performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the effect of Environmental practices on cash value added of firms listed on Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the effect of Social practices on cash value added of firms listed on Nigeria.
3. Evaluate the effect of corporate governance practices on cash value added of firms listed on Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Performance

The impact of environmental management activities on competitiveness and corporate economic success has been debated actively for many years. Financial and non-financial indices can directly reflect economic performance. Financial indices refer to sales, profitability, inventory turnover and return on equity while non-financial indices refer to market share, sale region and the number of customers (Earnhart & Lizal, 2010).

The Economic indicator used in ASSET4 ESG is non-financial based. The economic performance measures a company's capacity to produce feasible development and a high return on investment through the efficient use of all its resources. It demonstrates a company's ability to improve its margins by increasing its performance (production process innovations) or by maintaining a loyal and productive employee and supplier base. The company's capacity is also to maintain a loyal shareholder by creating reasonable returns through a focused and transparent long-term communications strategy with its shareholders. The customer fulfillment and dependability produce feasible and long-term revenue growth (Thomson Reuters, 2015).

Typically corporate environmental management practices relate to economic performance. By adopting new environmental practices such as reduce pollution source, more environmentally friendly ways of operation, etc., it can reduce waste disposal costs and penalty, thus, bringing about effective economic benefits for enterprises (Aragón-Correa, et al 2008). However, inconsistent findings were found in the empirical literature on the relationship between the environmental, social and economic performance. There is little evidence of a weak relationship and some for a weak but statistically significant positive relationship, negative to insignificant to moderately or even strongly positive relationships of environmental and economic performance (Orlitzky, Schmidt, & Rynes, 2003). Margolis and Walsh (2003) reported that most studies support a positive correlation between the environmental performance and economic performance.

Environment Disclosure

The interplay between the environment (viewed from an environmental perspective) in which business organizations operate and their financial performance is also disputed in literature, with diverging results from various studies over time. According to the neoclassical theory, improved environmental performance leads to increased costs. The idea stems from the fact that by reducing pollution and improving the environment, one can achieve a marginal decrease in net benefits. Porter (1991), however, argues that compliance with environmental regulations can benefit all implicated parties. Thus, both social welfare and private benefits of companies are on an upward trend. In the same paradigm Ambec et al. (2013) suggested that it can be considered that pollution is equated to a waste of resources, a reduction of which can lead to an improvement in the resources use efficiency. In other words, we can state that innovation is a catalyst for the sustainable activities of business organizations (Noja, et al. 2024). The environmental practices are being measure based on a company's management commitment and effectiveness towards reducing environmental emissions, efficient use of natural resources in the production and operational processes and the involvement of the company in supporting the research and development of eco-efficient products or services (Indarawati, Ruhanita & Nor, 2016).

Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSR)

The perception of corporate social responsibility seems to be as old as the business itself (Ferramosca & Verona, 2020), CSR was conceptually formalized by Bowen (1953), his proposed definition of the concept being the obligations of business people to pursue those policies, make those decisions, or follow those courses of action which are desirable in terms of the aims and values of our society. Many authors argue for the need to take a strategic view of CSR, highlighting criticisms of the characteristics of the traditional approach to CSR and arguing for its consideration as a core of a firm's strategy (Maury, 2022; Perez-Batres et al., 2012; Werther & Chandler, 2011). In that way, CSR can be viewed as a part of the business strategy that can improve financial and market performance (Berber et al., 2022).

The links between corporate social performance and financial performance are still far from being clarified in literature and contradictory evidence expressing the relationship between them is noted, both in intensity and sign (Lahouel et al., 2021). Results from empirical work indicate an ambiguous relationship between them (Ho et al., 2021; Jacobs et al., 2016). One fundamental reason for the uncertainty about this relationship is the problem of measuring social performance, which is a multi-dimensional construction that refers to a wide variety of topics. Their aggregation into a single form of measurement may suffer from inconsistency or lack of accuracy (Wang et al., 2015).

Corporate Governance

The emergence and further development of the concept of corporate governance have been associated with companies' constant attempts to improve their business in an increasingly dynamic competitive

environment (Noja, et al, 2024). The concept of corporate governance has received multiple meanings over time, being associated with management, accounting or auditing. It has often been used to describe actions taken to guide, direct and govern companies towards achieving business objectives.

The existence of a link between corporate governance and company performance has been addressed in a multitude of studies, with different findings, mainly attributable to differences in the theoretical basis of the research and the variables considered assessing corporate governance. Drobetz et al. (2004) highlighted the positive link between corporate governance and market performance, expressed by Tobin's Q ratio, results later confirmed by other studies (Strenger, 2017). Using the same performance evaluation indicator, Kiel and Nicholson (2003) found a positive relationship between the proportions of directors elected from within the company (as an indicator of good governance practices) and the performance of companies listed on the Australian stock exchange in 1996. Dahya et al. (2008) demonstrated a positive correlation between the proportion of independent directors and Tobin's Q ratio using a sample of companies with a shareholding of at least 10% of voting rights in 22 countries, with the link being stronger for countries with low shareholder protection.

Empirical Studies

Cao, Duan, and Ibrahim (2024) analyzed the effect of corporate underinvestment on environmental, social, and governance performance of Chinese A-listed companies from the period 2011 to 2020. The data were analysed using OLS and two-stage least squares methods. The study revealed a negative correlation between underinvestment and ESG ratings, particularly in the environmental and social dimensions. Kim and Lee (2023) determined the association between earnings announcement behaviours and ESG Performances'. A sample of 17,370 firm-quarters of firms listed in Korean stock markets was employed. The data were analysed using OLS technique. The study revealed a negative association between earnings announcement and ESG scores. Rahmatulloh and Suranta (2023) evaluated the effect of Environmental, Social, and Corporate Governance (ESG) performance on overall performance a company in Indonesian Stock Exchange spanning from 2018 to 2022, using financial performance (ROA), profitability (ROE), and Tobin's Q, which are regarded as reliance variables. Data were analyzed with multiple linear regression techniques. The study revealed that the ESG index exerts a positive and statistically significant influence on ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q. it showed that earnings management does not possess the capacity to moderate the relationship between ESG and company performance. Enekwe, Ugwudioha and Uyagu (2023) ascertained the effect of environmental costs on the financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria, using four listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria for a ten-year period from 2010 to 2019. The Panel Ordinary Least Square of the multiple regression model was conducted using the E-views version 9.0 statistical software package. The result showed that staff development costs have a negative but insignificant effect on listed Nigerian oil and gas companies'

return on assets, while community development costs and employee health and safety costs have a positive but insignificant effect. Okoye and Erinugha (2023) determined the effect of environmental disclosure on the financial performance of listed Oil and Gas companies in Nigeria for eleven (11) years spanning from 2011 to 2021, using health and safety disclosure, waste management disclosure, and environmental protection disclosure on cash value added. Panel data were extracted from audited annual reports and accounts of eleven (11) listed Oil and Gas companies. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data and inferential statistics was employed using Pearson correlation coefficient and Panel least square regression analysis to test the hypotheses of the study. The study indicated that there is a significant and positive association between employee health and safety disclosure, waste management disclosure, environmental protection disclosure and cash value added. Adeneye and Kammoun (2022) analyzed real earnings management and capital structure: Does environmental, social and governance (ESG) performance matter? period 2014-2019. Data were analysed using fixed effects panel data estimator. The study showed that REM has a significant positive effect on leverage. Also REM from abnormal production costs and abnormal discretionary expenses have positive and significantly affect leverage. Also, REM significantly and positively affects leverage in firms with low ESG performance and across ESG pillar scores. However, REM does not affect leverage in high- ESG performing firms, except for the governance pillar score. Fazle, Ruzlin and Jeaneth (2021) determined the effect of sustainability (environmental, social and governance or ESG) practices on the financial performance (FP) of the Nordic financial industry. The study covers a sample of 152 firm years for 39 financial companies within the Nordic region (Sweden, Denmark, Finland and Norway) from 2015 to 2019. Data regarding ESG and FP indicators were extracted from the Thomson Reuters Eikon database in July 2020. This is a quantitative study using regression and a generalized method of moments. Using static and dynamic estimators, the study found both positive and negative effect of sustainability practice on financial performance. The authors identified a negative relationship between ESG practices and FP (return on invested capital, return on equity and earnings per share). Chiamogu and Okoye (2020) evaluated the effect of environmental costs on the financial performance of Nigerian oil and gas companies from 2008 to 2018. Purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of sample size and E-views version 9.0 statistic software was employed for the running of the panel regression analysis. The environmental cost is an independent variable measured by community development cost (CDC) and environmental remediation cost (ERC), with two control variables as firm size (FSZ) and leverage (LEV), while financial performance is a dependent variable measured by Tobin's Q (TQ). The regression analysis showed that community development costs (CDC) and environmental remediation costs (ERC) have a positive and significant effect on Tobin's Q of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Osazefua (2019) ascertained of operational efficiency on the financial sustainability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. data were generated from 2009 to 2016 for 16 listed manufacturing companies and analyzed using Ordinary Least Square method.

The finding revealed that in relation to ROA, operating expenses and asset turnover had negative and positive significant relationship respectively. Employees' growth, account receivables, turnover, and inventory turnover was found to be insignificant. In relation to Tobin's Q, both inventory and asset turnover had a positive significant relationship. Nguyen and Tran (2019) studied the association between disclosure levels of environmental accounting information and financial performance. Data were extracted from the firms listed in Vietnam Stock Exchange from 2013 to 2017. The study used two regression models to investigate the relationship between environmental accounting information and return on assets. The study indicated that there was a close relationship between disclosure level of environmental accounting information and financial performance. Tafadzwa and Fortune (2019) ascertained the association between corporate sustainability disclosure and return on investment in ten Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE)-listed mining companies from 2010 to 2014. A multi-regression analysis was used to analyze the relationship between environmental disclosure and return on investment. Results showed that there is a negative relationship between environmental disclosure and return on investment. On the other hand, the research revealed that there is also a positive association between social disclosure and return on investment. Falope, Offor and Ofurum (2019) examined Environmental Cost Disclosure and Corporate Performance of Quoted Construction Firms in Nigeria *Ex-post facto* ROA Environmental pollution control cost Environmental protection cost Environmental cost resource recycling. The findings showed that environmental pollution prevention cost, environmental protection cost and environmental recycling disclosure have effects on return on assets of quoted construction firms in Nigeria. Mohammed (2018) determined the volume of environmental disclosure of listed Nigerian oil and gas companies for six (6) years pre- and six (6) years post IFRS adoption using quantity modified word count content analysis on yearly reports of the sampled companies. Two sample t-tests statistical method was used to detect the statistical mean of the pre and post IFRS period of quantity environmental disclosure. Panel Corrected Standard Error Regression analysis is used to determine the influence of corporate characteristics on the volume of the disclosure. Panel regression analysis results show that corporate size, have positive and significant relationship with disclosure. Obtained results are perhaps consistent with legitimacy theory. Odoemelam and Okafor (2018) investigated the influence of corporate governance on environmental disclosure of nonfinancial firms listed in Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), anchoring on "Trinity theory" (agency, stakeholder and legitimacy theories). 86 firm-year observations across 86 companies listed in Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) using content analysis, cross-sectional data, OLS regression techniques were used to analyze the influence of board characteristics on the extent of overall environmental disclosure (OED). The results show that board independence, board meeting, and the environmental committee were statistically significant while audit committee independence and board size were insignificant.

Methodology

The study employed Ex-Post Facto research design and content analysis. The panel nature of the data implies that the cross sectional research design is also applied because the sample objects of the study cover different firms for various years in order to determine their relationships and how significant one variable affects another.

Population and Sampled Size

A sample of eleven (11) manufacturing companies was selected from a total of forty nine (64) manufacturing firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX), using purposive sampling.

Methods and Sources of Data

The study used secondary data which were sourced from the various annual reports of the sampled manufacturing firms deposited in the libraries and website of the NGX. The research covered a period of twelve (12) financial years (2012-2023). The twelve-year period was used for the estimations in order to use information from the same accounting reporting regime (that is, IFRS) – especially since Nigeria adopted IFRS in 2012.

Model Specification

This study modified the model proposed by Yasin and **Evren (2021)**. The model specified by, Yasin and **Evren (2021)** are as follows:

$$FRQ_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 ESG_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 ROA_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \beta_5 FIRM_AGE_{it} + \Sigma YEAR + \Sigma INDUSTRY + \Sigma COUNTRY + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where:

FRQ_{it} = separately represents the models FRQ1, FRQ, FRQ 3 and FRQ 4

ESG_{it} = separately represents ESG, ENV, SOC, and GOV

SIZE_{it} = the natural logarithm of the market value of equity

ROA_{it} = Return on assets

LEV_{it} = Total liabilities/total assets

FIRM_AGE_{it} = The natural logarithm of 1 + age of firm

The model was modified as follows:

$$CVA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EVD_{i,t} + \beta_2 FSIZ_{i,t} + e_{it} \dots\dots\dots i$$

$$CVA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SPD_{i,t} + \beta_2 FSIZ_{i,t} + e_{it} \dots\dots\dots ii$$

$$CVA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GVD_{i,t} + \beta_2 FSIZ_{i,t} + e_{it} \dots\dots\dots iii$$

Where:

ENV_{it}= environmental-related disclosures of firm *i* at period *t*.

SPD_{it}= social-related practices disclosures of firm *i* at period *t*.

GOV_{it}= governance-related disclosure of firm *i* at period *t*.

FSIZE_{it} = Natural logarithm of total assets of firm *i* at period *t*.

B₀ = Intercept

β₁ – β₄ = are the parameters to be estimated in the equation

e = Stochastic error term.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed with descriptive statistics, and the hypotheses were tested inferential statistics (Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis). Since the focus of the study is to determine the significant effect, regression analysis becomes appropriate tool for it.

i. Descriptive statistics employed to summarily describe the mean, median, standard deviation, kurtosis and skewness of the study variables. Inferential statistics was also be utilized with the aid of E-Views 9 using:

ii. Regression analysis: Regression analysis predicts the value the dependent variable based on the value of the independent variable and explains the impact or effect of changes in the values of the variables.

Decision Rule

The decision for the hypotheses is to accept the alternative hypotheses if the p-value of the test statistic is less or equal than the alpha and to reject the alternative hypotheses if the p-value of the test statistic is greater than alpha at 5% significance level.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	CVA	EVD	SPD	GVD	LFZS
Mean	3419741.	20.83333	65.00000	48.33333	7.588763
Median	762306.5	25.00000	60.00000	60.00000	7.635208
Maximum	19826949	25.00000	90.00000	60.00000	7.776074
Minimum	-431601.0	12.50000	50.00000	20.00000	7.439775
Std. Dev.	6060259.	5.915004	11.22293	17.30581	0.096110
Skewness	1.914513	-0.707107	0.715542	-0.912527	-0.101770
Kurtosis	5.121068	1.500000	2.920000	1.968119	2.366286
Jarque-Bera	105.3821	23.37500	11.29920	24.17580	2.436622
Probability	0.000000	0.000008	0.003519	0.000006	0.295729
Sum	4.51E+08	2750.000	8580.000	6380.000	1001.717
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.81E+15	4583.333	16500.00	39233.33	1.210061
Observations	132	132	132	132	132

Source: E-views 9 (2025)

From Table .1, it could be observed that the mean values of the cash value added (CVA) stood at 3419741.0. It implied that the Nigerian CVA was enough cash value added. Furthermore, the mean value of environmental disclosure (EVD) run using the dummy value of GRI showed an average value of 20.833.

Also, the mean values of corporate social responsibility disclosure (SPD) showed that Nigerian SPD were jointly 56.00. On the variable of governance disclosure (GVD), the mean values stood at 48.333 which implied that firms maintained optimum disclosure. The mean values of GVD suggested that the Nigerian sampled firms had more number of disclosures.

Similarly, the mean values of the control variable, firm size (LFSZ) showed that about 7.589% of Nigerian firms.

The kurtosis of 5.121068, 1.500000, 2.920000, 1.968119, and 2.366286, for Nigerian firms CVA, EVD, SPD, GVD and LFSZ showing a distribution that is strong, suggesting a concentration of values around the mean with potential outliers. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.000000 0.000008 0.003519 0.000006 0.295729 confirms that the CVA, EVD, SPD, GVD and LFSZ data is significantly non-normally distributed showed that traditional parametric analyses may need to be approached with caution.

On the Jarque–Bera test of goodness-of-fit, the result suggested that only the data on firms in the Nigerian and Ghanaian sample firms followed a normal distribution. However, the departure from normality of the other variables did not pose any major problem in the panel data since the Central Limit Theorem revealed that the violation of the normality assumption posed no major problem in panel data analysis, especially with large firm-year observations (Ghasem and Zahediasl, 2012).

Multivariate Analyses

For the panel regressions, both fixed and random effects procedures were estimated for both models. However, the standard procedure for panel data analysis requires the Hausman test for the selection of the most appropriate model for statistical inference between the fixed and random effects models. The decision rule for the Hausman tests is to accept H_1 when the p-value is less than 5%. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that the Fixed Effect Model is consistent while the null hypothesis (H_0), that is the Random Effect Model is consistent. The Hausman test results of the models were presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Hausman Test Results

(Nigeria)	Model 1		
Test	Chi-Sq.	Chi-Sq.	Prob.
Summary	Statistic	d.f.	
Cross-section random	0.000000	4	1.0000

NOTE: *insignificant, showing desirability of the random effect models

As could be observed from Table 2, the corresponding probability values of the chi-squared statistic in both models were both higher than 5% (p-value=1.0000). This showed the suitability of the random effect models. It implied that the random effect model was preferred to the fixed effect model in the

insignificant results while the latter was considered suitable in capturing the relationships and drawing inferences in both model.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: Environmental practice has no significant effect on cash value added of firms listed on Nigeria Exchange Group

Table 3: Regression analysis between EVD, LFSZ and CVD (Nigeria)

Dependent Variable: CVA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 02/16/25 Time: 21:39

Sample: 2012 2023

Periods included: 12

Cross-sections included: 11

Total panel (balanced) observations: 132

Variable	Coefficien t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.69E+08	28501182	-5.916751	0.0000
EVD	-571106.7	59921.32	-9.530943	0.0000
LFZS	24240077	3687809.	6.573029	0.0000
R-squared	0.626817	Mean dependent var	3419741.	
Adjusted squared	R-		6060259	
S.E. of regression	0.621031	S.D. dependent var	.	
Sum squared resid	3730724.	Akaike info criterion	33.12457	
Log likelihood	-2183.221	Schwarz criterion	9	
F-statistic	108.3372	Hannan-Quinn		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	critere.	33.15119	
		Durbin-Watson stat	2	
			2.29389	

In table 3 showed a simple least square regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between environmental disclosures (EVD) and cash value added (CVA) for Nigerian and Ghanaian

manufacturing firms respectively. The R-squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. From the findings, R squared was 0.62, an indication that there was variation of 62% on EVD due to changes in CVA. This implies that 62% changes in EVD could be accounted for by CVA, while 38% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 2.29 suggests that the model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 108.337. The associated F-statistic probability is equal to 0.000.

The evidence provided by the regression result of model showed that the variable of environmental disclosure had a negative coefficient of -571106.7 and a p-value of 0.000 which was significant at 5% level. It meant that there was a significant effect between environmental disclosure and cash value added in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 11

Ho₂: Social practices have no significant effect on cash value added of firms listed on Nigeria Exchange Group

Table 4: Regression analysis between CSPD, LFSZ and CVD

Dependent Variable: CVA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 02/16/25 Time: 21:42

Sample: 2012 2023

Periods included: 12

Cross-sections included: 11

Total panel (balanced) observations: 132

Variable	Coefficien t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.90E+08	32317751	-8.968191	0.0000
CSR	119262.6	36449.95	3.271955	0.0014
LFZS	37621343	4256330.	8.838917	0.0000
R-squared	0.412764	Mean dependent var	3419741.	
Adjusted squared	R-0.403659	S.D. dependent var	.	6060259
S.E. of regression	4679919.	Akaike info criterion	33.57792	
Sum squared resid	2.83E+15	Schwarz criterion	33.6434	

		Hannan-Quinn	4
			33.6045
Log likelihood	-2213.143	critier.	5
F-statistic	45.33656	Durbin-Watson stat	1.880615
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

In table 4, a simple least square regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between Social practices disclosure (CSPD) and cash value added (CVA) for Nigeria. The R-squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. From the findings, Adjusted R-squared was 0.40, an indication that there was variation of 40% on CSPD due to changes in CVA. This implies that 40% changes in SPD could be accounted for by CVA, while 60% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 1.881 suggests that the both model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 45.337. The associated F-statistic probability is equal to 0.000.

The evidence provided by the regression result of model 1 showed that the variable of social practice disclosure had a positive coefficient of 119262.6 and a p-value of 0.001 which was significant at 5% level for Nigeria manufacturing firms. It meant that there was a significant effect between social practice disclosure and cash value added in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 111

Ho₃: Corporate governance practice has no significant effect on cash value added of firms listed on Nigeria Exchange Group.

Table 5: Regression analysis between GVD, LFSZ and CVD

Dependent Variable: CVA
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 02/16/25 Time: 21:43
 Sample: 2012 2023
 Periods included: 12
 Cross-sections included: 11
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 132

Variable	Coefficien	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.20E+08	27983780	-4.289073	0.0000	

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

	-			
GVD	226883.4	20114.54	-11.27957	0.0000
LFZS	17711746	3621880.	4.890208	0.0000
<hr/>				
R-squared	0.679816	Mean dependent var	3419741.	
Adjusted squared	R-		6060259	
S.E. of regression	0.674852	S.D. dependent var	.	
Sum squared resid	3455664.	Akaike info criterion	32.97139	
	1.54E+15	Schwarz criterion	33.03691	
		Hannan-Quinn	32.9980	
Log likelihood	-2173.112	crit.	2	
			2.73039	
F-statistic	136.9470	Durbin-Watson stat	2	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
<hr/>				

Table 5, showed a simple least square regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between governance practices disclosure (GVD) and cash value added (CVA) in Nigeria The R-squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. The Adjusted R-squared was 0.67, indicating that there was 67% changes on GVD due to changes in CVA. This implies that 67% changes in GVD could be accounted for by CVA, while 33% was explained by other variables not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 2.730, suggests that the both model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 136.947, and the associated F-statistic probability is equal to 0.000.

The evidence provided by the regression result of model 1 showed that the variable of governance practices disclosure had a negative coefficient of -226883.4 and a p-value of 0.000 which was significant at 5% level for Nigeria manufacturing firms. It meant that there was a significant effect between governance practices disclosure and cash value added in Nigerian manufacturing firms, while there was no significant effect between governance practices disclosure and cash value added in Ghanaian manufacturing firms, howbeit negatively and positively respectively.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study determined the effect of environmental, social and governance practices on performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, using environmental practices, Social practices and corporate governance practices as the independent variables and cash value added for dependent variable. Hypotheses were tested inferential statistics regression analysis. From the hypotheses results, environmental disclosure had a negative coefficient but statistically significant at 5% level for Nigeria

manufacturing firms; Social practice disclosure had a positive coefficient which was significant at 5% level for Nigeria manufacturing firms; Governance practices disclosure had a negative coefficient but was significant at 5% level for Nigeria manufacturing firms. Company's sustainability performance as shown by the ESG performance consists of the environmental, social, and governance aspects that must be maintained and improved from time to time.

While the significance of specific ESG components varies, they all contribute to the creation of long-term shareholder value. Companies that embrace ESG concerns not only align with changing societal expectations, but they also stand to improve their reputations, attract ethical investors, and ultimately contribute to the long-term increase of shareholder value. It is therefore safe to conclude that ESG variables and shareholder wealth emerges as a fundamental need for firms seeking long-term success in today's dynamic corporate market in Nigeria.

Based on the outcome of the study, the following are our recommendations:

1. Nigerian government need to improve on the Environmental performance evaluation system due to the imperfection of the Environmental disclosure system, hence the Environmental information reported by some enterprises may be false.
2. Though the social disclosure revealed positive significant, Nigerian government agencies should make corresponding penalties for enterprises with poor social practice performance and put forward equivalent refinement ideas for enterprises with good social practice.
3. Manufacturing firms should place more emphasis on comprehensive disclose of their corporate governance activities as investors place more confidence on this disclosure parameter.

References

- Adeneye, Y., & Kammoun, I. (2022). Real earnings management and capital structure: Does environmental, social and governance (ESG) performance matter?. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 2130134
- Aragón-Correa, J. A. Hurtado-Torres, N. Sharma, S. and García-Morales, V. J. (2008). "Environmental strategy and performance in small firms: A resource-based perspective," *Journal of Environmental Management*, 86(1), 88–103, 2008. Reporting in Australia. *Australian Accounting Review*, 23(1), 67-87.
- Ambec, S., Cohen, M. A., Elgie, S., & Lanoie, P. (2013). The Porter hypothesis at 20: Can environmental regulation enhance innovation and competitiveness? *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 7, 2–22. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1682001>.

Berber, N., Aleksić, M., Slavić, A., & Strugar Jelača, M. (2022). The relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate reputation in Serbia. *Engineering Economics*, 33(3), 232–245. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.33.3.29316>

Busch, T., Stinchfield, B. T., & Wood, M. S. (2011). *A triptych inquiry: Rethinking sustainability, innovation, and financial performance* (Discussion Paper No. 11-026/2/DSF 9). Tinbergen Institute.

Cao, M., Duan, K., & Ibrahim, H. (2024). Corporate underinvestment and its effects on environmental, social, and governance performance. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-21.

Chang, Y.-J., & Lee, B.-H. (2022). The impact of ESG activities on firm value: Multi-level analysis of industrial characteristics. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14444. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114444>.

Chiamogu, A & Okoye, J.N (2020). Environmental Cost and Financial Performance of Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research for Social and Management Sciences*, 6(10), 1 – 24.

Cooper, W. W., Seiford, L. M., & Tone, K. (2006). *Introduction to data envelopment analysis and its uses: with DEA-solver software and references*: Springer Science & Business Media

Dahya, J., Dimitrov, O., & McConnell, J. J. (2008). Dominant shareholders, corporate boards, and corporate value: A cross-country analysis. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 87(1), 73–100.

Drobetz, W., Schillhofer, A., & Zimmermann, H. (2004). Corporate governance and expected stock returns: Evidence from Germany. *European Financial Management*, 10(2), 267–293. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1354-7798.2004.00250.x>

Earnhart, D. and Lizal, L. (2010). Effect of corporate economic performance on firm-level environmental performance in a transition economy,” *Environmental and Resource Economics*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 303–329,

Enekwe, C.I., Ugwudioha, O. M. & Uyagu, B. D. (2023). Effect of environmental costs on the financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 8(1), 2023, 31-36 ISSN: 2617-9954 Open Access Journal Research Article Homepage: www.j.arabianjbmr.com AOJP. IJAR | j.arabianjbmr.com © 2023, Authors, ZARSMI.

- Falope, F.J &Offor, N.T. (2019). Environmental Cost Disclosure and Corporate Performance of Quoted Construction Firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 5(8), 17-31
- Ferramosca, S., & Verona, R. (2020). Framing the evolution of corporate social responsibility as a discipline (1973–2018): A large-scale scientometric analysis. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 27(1), 178–203. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1792>
- Homburg, C. (2001). Using data envelopment analysis to benchmark activities. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 73(1), 51-58.
- Ho, J., Lu, C., & Lucianetti, L. (2021). Does engaging in corporate social responsibility activities influence firm performance? The moderating effects of risk preferences and performance measurement systems. *Management Decision*, 59(13), 15–37. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-07-2020-0925>.
- Indarawati T., Ruhanita M. & Nor H. T. (2016). The Impact of Environmental, Social and Governance Practices (ESG) on Economic Performance: Evidence from ESG Score. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, Vol. 7, No. 3, June 2016
- Jacobs, B. W., Kraude, R., & Narayanan, S. (2016). Operational productivity, corporate social performance, financial performance, and risk in manufacturing firms. *Production and Operations Management*, 25(12), 2065–2085. <https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.12596>
- Kim, J., & Lee, Y. (2023). Association between Earnings Announcement Behaviors and ESG Performances. *Sustainability*, 15(9), 7733.
- Lahouel, B. B., Zaied, Y. B., Song, Y., & Yang, G. (2021). Corporate social performance and financial performance relationship: A data envelopment analysis approach without explicit input. *Finance Research Letters*, 39, 101656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2020.101656>
- Mohammed, S. D. (2018). Mandatory social and environmental disclosure: A performance evaluation of listed Nigerian oil and gas companies pre- and post-mandatory disclosure requirements. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*. 6(2), 56-68. <file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/10.11648.j.jfa.20180602.12.pdf>

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June 2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Maury, B. (2022). Strategic CSR and firm performance: The role of prospector and growth strategies. *Journal of Economic and Business*, 118, 106031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconbus.2021.106031>
- Margolis J. D. and Walsh, J. P. (2003). Misery loves rethinking companies: Social initiatives by business,” *Administrative Science Quarterly*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 268–305,
- Nasrallah, N. and El Khoury, R. (2021), “Is corporate governance a good predictor of SMEs financial performance? Evidence from developing countries (the case of Lebanon)”, *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment*, doi: [10.1080/20430795.2021.1874213](https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2021.1874213). (accessed April 2021).
- Nguyen, L & Tran, M. (2019). Disclosure Levels of Environmental Accounting Information and Financial Performance: The case of Vietnam. *Management Science Letters*, 9(4), 557-570
- Noja, G. G., Baditoiu, B. R., Buglea, A., Munteanu, V. P., & Gligor Cimpoiu, D. C. (2024). The impact of environmental, social and governance policies on companies' financial and economic performance: A comprehensive approach and new empirical evidence. *E&M Economics and Management*, 27(1), 121–144. <https://doi.org/10.15240/tul/001/2024-1-008>
- Okoye. I. E. & Erinugha, C. F. (2023). Environmental Disclosure: A Study of Financial Performance of Listed Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(4), 2544-2552, April 2023. Journal homepage: www.ijrpr.com ISSN 2582-7421
- Osazefua, I. J. (2019). Operational efficiency and financial sustainability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 11 (1), 17-31.
- Orlitzky, M., & Benjamin, J. D. (2001). Corporate social performance and firm risk: A meta-analytic review. *Business and Society*, 40(4), 369–396. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000765030104000402>
- Orlitzky, M., Schmidt, F.L. and Rynes, S.L. (2003), “Corporate social and financial performance: a metaanalysis”, *Organization Studies*, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 403-441.
- Odoemelam, N. & Okafor, R. G. (2018). The influence of corporate governance on environmental disclosure of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. *Indonesian Journal of Sustainability Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 25–49. <http://unpas.id/index.php/ijsam>

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June 2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Perez-Batres, L. A., Doh, J. P., Miller, V. V., & Pisani, M. J. (2012). Stakeholder pressures as determinants of CSR strategic choice: Why do firms choose symbolic versus substantive self-regulatory codes of conduct? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 110(2), 157–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1419-y>
- Porter, M. E. (1991). America's green strategy. *Business and the Environment: A Reader*, 33, 1072.
- Porter, M. E., & Kramer, M. R. (2002). The competitive advantage of corporate philanthropy. *Harvard Business Review*, 80(12), 56–68.
- Rahcmatulloh, R., & Suranta, E. (2023). The Effect of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) on Firm Performance With Earnings Management As a Moderation: Empirical Evidence Around COVID–19. *Ilomata International Journal of Tax and Accounting*, 4(4), 846-862. <https://doi.org/10.52728/ijtc.v4i4.937>.
- Strenger, C. (2017). *Study of the German corporate governance code compliance*. Harvard Law School Forum on Corporate Governance. <https://corpgov.law.harvard.edu/2018/09/18/study-of-the-german-corporate-governance-code-compliance/>
- Tafadzwa, M. W. & Fortune, G. (2019). Relationship between Corporate Sustainability Disclosure and Firm Financial Performance in Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) Listed Mining Companies. *Africa Centre for Sustainability Accounting and Management (ACSAM) Journal*. 11(4496), 2-23
- Thomson Reuters. (2015). Thomson Reuter's data stream ASSET 4 ESG content. URL. [Online]. Available:
http://extranet.datastream.com/data/ASSET4%20ESG/documents/Thomson_Reuters_DS_ASSET4_ESG_Content_Fact_Sheet_April_2015.pdf
- Velte, P. (2019). The bidirectional relationship between ESG performance and earnings management—empirical evidence from Germany. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 10(4), 322-338.
- Veenstra, E. M., & Ellemers, N. (2020). ESG indicators as organizational performance goals: Do rating agencies encourage a holistic approach? *Sustainability*, 12(24), 10228. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410228>

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June 2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Wang, Q., Wu, C., & Sun, Y. (2015). Evaluating corporate social responsibility of airlines using entropy weight and grey relation analysis. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 42, 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2014.08.003>.

Werther, W. B., & Chandler, D. (2011). *Strategic corporate social responsibility: Stakeholders in a global society* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications Inc.